

Cassette
505

an injury, dancer Kalya Yannatos will not appear tonight and
"Simultaneous Contrasts" for Horn and Dancer by James Yannatos has been
removed from the program. The revised program is as follows.

* * REVISED PROGRAM * *

THE CLEVELAND INSTITUTE OF MUSIC
Wednesday, October 4, 1989
8:00 p.m., Kulas Hall

Guest Artist Recital

ERIC RUSKE, Horn

assisted by

ANNE EPPERSON, Piano
DAVID ZAUDER, Trumpet
JAMES DESANO, Trombone

SCHUMANN	Adagio and Allegro, Op. 70	8:49 +1 +1
BACH transc. Ruske	Sonata for Horn and Piano in G. Minor (Sonata No. 3 for Viola da Gamba, BWV 1029)	14:31
	Vivace Adagio Allegro	-2 (R)
ADLER	Sonata for Horn and Piano	
	Andante con moto Allegro scherzando Moderato ma non appassionata Allegro con fuoco	8:42 x2 +2
MENDELSSOHN transc. Ruske	"Song Without Words" in D Major, Op. 109	-1 4:34
POULENC	Sonata for Trumpet, Trombone and Horn	7:29
PERSICETTI	Parable VIII for Solo Horn	-5 -3 +2 +2 6:51
DUKAS	Villanelle for Horn and Piano	-2 0 6:36

INTERMISSION

Trumpeter, DAVID ZAUDER has been a member of The Cleveland Orchestra since 1958 and has simultaneously held the position of The Orchestra's Personnel Manager since 1971. He has performed as Principal Trumpet of the Boston Pops, under Arthur Fiedler, and as Solo Cornet with the Leonard B. Smith Concert Band of Detroit. A recipient of degrees in humanities and business administration from Western Reserve University, he is the author of a trumpet embouchure study method used widely in the U.S. and abroad. He has performed as a clinician for the King Musical Instrument Company. A former member of the faculty of the Detroit Institute of Music, he was appointed to the faculty of The Cleveland Institute of Music in 1979 where he has served as Professor of Trumpet and Chairman of the Brass Division.

JAMES DESANO is Principal Trombone of The Cleveland Orchestra as well as a member of the Severance Brass Quintet and the Cleveland Low Brass Ensemble. He holds a Bachelor of Science degree in music education from Ithaca College and was a student of Emory Remington. He served as Principal Trombone of the Syracuse Symphony and brass quintet and has recorded with The Cleveland Symphonic Winds and numerous chamber ensembles. Former faculty appointments include Syracuse University, Oberlin College and The University of Akron. He was appointed to The Cleveland Institute of Music faculty in 1986 where he now serves as Head of the Trombone Department.

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CORRECTIONS

Upcoming Events at CIM

CAROL RUZICKA, Violin, Faculty Recital
Sunday, October 15, La Pavillon
3:00 p.m. (NOT 8:00 p.m.)

CIM CONTEMPORARY MUSIC ENSEMBLE
Sunday, October 29, Kulas Hall
4:00 p.m. (NOT 8:00 p.m.)